

Lighting talk submission: Explainable entity matching for library metadata

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We present a study on the practical value of explainable AI for an entity-matching model, with its outputs assessed by domain experts. Entity matching is critical for improving information retrieval and interoperability of cultural heritage data. Digital archives and libraries often contain data from heterogeneous sources, using different metadata-standards. Grouping records in bibliographic databases under canonical umbrella entities allows users to easily select and compare translations, adaptations and revised editions of the same work. Inspired by previous success of zero-shot performance on the task of entity-matching in other contexts [6], we evaluated LLM performance in the context of entity-matching of bibliographic metadata from the KB National Library of the Netherlands [1]. To do this we used a subset of the national bibliography, and created a challenge set consisting of edge-cases, those pairs of book records which were difficult to match. We evaluated various LLMs under different conditions and prompt strategies. We have shown that LLMs can help structure metadata and group book items together when they contain the same ‘work’. The library intends to use such an entity-matching system to support catalogers with a full human-in-the-loop workflow. Because human experts have more trust in generated labels when supported by explanations [3], an explainable AI (X-AI) component could be desirable. To continue our work, we thus want to answer the following question: Can X-AI/explanations help catalogers to get insights in difficult entity-matching cases, to detect potential errors in the labeling? And what would the best way to support human computer interaction?

X-AI methods specific for entity matching have been explored in previous literature [2, 5]. These methods can currently only be applied to smaller entity-matching PLMs (pre-trained language models), as they require a large number of permutations for each potential record pair. We fine-tune PLMs on a subset of

the national bibliography, part of which has been checked by hand by catalogers. The methods used to generate explanations are evaluated via a user study. We ask expert catalogers from the KB national library to assess the output of the PLM matching model with the help of different explanations. We use a survey to record their preferences. To better assess the value of X-AI implementations, we additionally compare the matching accuracy of the explainable PLMs, a fully transparent rule-based grouping tool, and non-explainable LLMs. This work therefore offers new insights into the practical use and trade-offs of explainable entity matching in a large-scale cultural heritage domain.

We are currently fine-tuning a PLM [4], and have tested out the explainable entity-matching method LEMON on the model. We aim to update the challenge set from our previous paper to investigate future performance of our models. We are in close cooperation with the national library of Anonymous and their catalogers, whose input is vital for the actual evaluation of these systems designed to assist them in their cataloging process.

References

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